

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

German farmers intention to apply underseeding

Farmers' perceptions of soil quality are of high importance in developing more sustainable farming practices. The farmer survey implemented in the SoildiverAgro project identified relevant agri-environmental problems in current production and the most effective farming practices to address these issues. The survey data was collected from six different regions in Europe. In Finland, 200 farmers responded to the survey, with 91% being conventional farmers and 9% organic.

In Germany, the survey measured farmers' interest in applying underseeding on their farms. Of the respondents, 15% were certainly interested in applying it in the future, 27% were hesitant, and 59% were negative.

In Germany, the costs and need for plant protections were emphasized in evaluating the impacts of underseeding. However, reduction in erosion was also perceived as an important effect of the practice. Peer farmers' as well as consulting services opinions were seen as encouraging the use of the practice. As a controlling factor, farmers perceived costs of the practice as influential but also policy instruments, especially the possibility of subsidies. The intention to use the practice in the future was particularly determined by previous experiences and attitudes towards the practice.

1. *Undersowing promotes soil biodiversity but requires extensive agricultural experience.*

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KEYWORDS

Underseeding, soil quality

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